

APPROACHES TO CONDUCTING INFORMATION SECURITY AUDITS

¹Fayziyeva D.S., ²Kholimtayeva I.U., ³Shamshiyeva B.M.

¹PhD, Tashkent University of Information Technologies

²Senior Teacher, Tashkent University of Information Technologies

³Senior Teacher, Tashkent University of Information Technologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14271900>

Abstract. *Information security auditing involves the assessment of the information security status of automated information systems and the development of recommendations for organizational measures and software-hardware tools aimed at protecting the information resources of these systems from security threats.*

Keywords: *white box, gray box, black box, technical lower system audits.*

Based on the analysis of information security audit, the following main approaches to audit can be identified:

- practical approach to audit;
- theoretical approach to audit.

The general classification of approaches is presented in Figure 1.

Practical approaches to audit

General practical approaches to audit include:

- risk analysis-based audit;
- audit based on analysis of information security standards;
- audit based on a combination of risk analysis and analysis of information security standards;
- audit based on experimental studies of the system or its prototype.

Risk analysis-based audit is carried out using formal risk analysis methods in the event that the auditor determines an individual set of information security requirements for the system under study, taking into account the specific features of the system, its operating environment and its characteristics as much as possible. This approach is the most labor-intensive and requires high theoretical skills from the auditor. The quality of the audit results is strongly influenced by the methodology of risk analysis and management, as well as its application to a specific type of the system under study. Risk analysis is the systematic use of data to identify risk sources and assess risk levels [10].

Risk analysis methods can be qualitative, semi-quantitative or quantitative. It should be noted that a full quantitative analysis of systems is not always possible due to the complexity of modern information systems, the difficulty of obtaining adequate statistical data on events, etc. Risk analysis includes the following stages [10]:

- inventory and categorization of system resources;
- identification of significant threats and vulnerabilities;
- assessment of the likelihood of threats and vulnerabilities.

An audit based on the analysis of information security standards is the most practical approach to auditing. Information security standards define a basic set of security requirements for a wide range of systems, which are formed as a result of generalizing world practice. Information

security standards can specify a set of different security requirements depending on the level of protection of the system under study, its affiliation (commercial organization or government agency) and purpose (finance, industry, communications, etc.). In this case, the auditor must correctly determine the set of standard requirements that a specific system under study must meet. Detailed information on conducting an audit based on the analysis of information security standards is provided in the literature [4, 10, 20].

Figure 1. Classification of common approaches to information security audit

A combined audit using risk analysis and information security standards is the most effective way to conduct an audit. The basic set of security requirements for the systems under study is determined by information security standards. Additional requirements are formed on the basis of risk analysis, taking into account the performance characteristics of a specific system. This approach is simpler than risk-based audit, since most of the information security requirements are already defined by standards, and at the same time it does not have the disadvantage of the second approach, i.e. standard requirements may not be taken into account, but take into account the specific features of certain systems.

Most audit works [4, 5, 9, 10, 20] show only these three approaches. In this case, the so-called "penetration test" [13] is distinguished. It differs from the above approaches in that it is a type of experimental study of the object, which, as a rule, is carried out with the aim of identifying weak points of protection or new vulnerabilities as a result of the implementation of new protective measures. According to the author, "penetration testing" is a specific variation of another general approach to audit - an audit based on an experimental study of the system or its prototype.

An examination of a system or its prototype based on experimental studies is carried out using the means or methods of ITT (information-technological threat) or IPT (information-psychological threat) against the system for the purpose of practical verification of the effectiveness of technical or organizational protection measures, as well as to identify new weak

points in the system. According to the level of attention to the technical or organizational-psychological sphere, this approach can be divided into the following:

- *audit of technical subsystems* - carried out for the purpose of practical assessment of the stability of technical means and methods of protection (both hardware and software) when targeted ITT is used against them, as well as the level of information security provided in such systems, conditions;

- *audit of organizational subsystems* - carried out for the purpose of practical assessment of organizational measures, information security rules, stability of the behavior of the organization and its employees when targeted IPT is used against the organization or security of information provided in such circumstances;

- *comprehensive audit* – conducted for the purpose of practical assessment of the level of information security provided in the conditions of targeted use of both ITT and IPT. According to the literature, this type of audit includes "penetration testing".

In some works, for example [10, 13, 18], the terms "active audit" or "instrumental audit" are used for this approach. However, in the author's opinion, these concepts are erroneous. Instrumental audit terminologically implies the study of a system using any "instrumental tools", which in some literatures are understood primarily as hardware (hardware or software), but not targeted ITT or IPT methods. The term "active audit" is more suitable for high-level influence in order to make the necessary changes to the object under study. However, this term does not include ITT and ITT conducted for reconnaissance purposes [1, 3].

Theoretical approaches to auditing

Depending on the formalization of the analysis process used, the following theoretical approaches to auditing exist [11, 12]:

- process approach:

- o Based on the IDEF0 methodology;
- o Based on the IDEF1 methodology;
- o Based on the IDEF2 methodology;
- o Based on the IDEF3 methodology;
- o Based on the IDEF4 methodology;

- Based on the assessment model;

- Based on the maturity model:

- o Based on the ISO/IEC 15504 standard "Information technology. Process assessment";
- o Based on the ISO/IEC 21827 standard "System security engineering - capability maturity model";

o Based on the COBIT standard (Objectives of information management and related technologies);

o Based on the URSIT standard (Unified interdepartmental rating system of information technology).

The process approach considers the activity on ensuring information security as an auxiliary process in the activities of the organization and its business processes [11]. This is due to the fact that the information security system, including related processes, does not participate directly in the target processes of the organization (for example, the release of a specific product), but, on the contrary, even increases the cost of the product, which, naturally, is expensive for the organization. At the same time, the costs of information security help to reduce potential losses

and thereby participate in the main business processes of the organization. Based on the process approach, organizational activity is represented as a set and hierarchy of the following three groups of target and auxiliary processes [11]:

- o management processes (organization's management processes);
- o main processes (target processes of the organization's activities);
- o auxiliary processes (processes related to the organization's resources).

These processes are formalized based on the IDEF (Integrated DEFinition) methodology - any are studied as a set of interacting and interrelated blocks reflecting the processes, operations, actions occurring in the system under study from the point of view of the system. The IDEF methodology distinguishes three levels of process description detail [11, 12]:

- o IDEF0 – formalizes processes taking into account their functions, hierarchy and logical connections between them;
- o IDEF1 – formalizes information processes taking into account their structure and interdependence;
- o IDEF2 – additionally takes into account the dynamics of processes, is formalized in the same way as IDEF0;
- o IDEF3 – each process can be additionally divided into separate functional blocks necessary for a detailed description of technological operations and formalizes processes in the same way as IDEF0;
- o IDEF4 – formalizes processes based on an object-oriented approach;

The approach based on the assessment model defines the list of assessed processes of the audited object and the reference model, defines the criteria and main audit indicators, as well as the method of assessing processes using these indicators and the method of presenting the assessment results. The basis of the assessment model is the list and model of the processes being assessed, as well as a set of indicators used to collect data and determine the level of achievement of the specified AX criteria [11]. This theoretical approach includes most practical approaches to auditing aimed at assessing information security indicators and checking their compliance with pre-defined criteria.

The maturity model approach (CMM) was developed in the software industry to assess the maturity of software development processes and identify key activities required for further development. The original CMM model has become a standard for assessing and improving software development processes. The basic SMM methodology defines criteria and 5 levels of process maturity: the first is "initial", characterized by the fact that some target activities are implemented, but not controlled, not formalized, etc., the fifth is "continuous improvement", the activity within the process is not only based on the best standards, but is also characterized by continuous improvement and optimization.

Later, with some modifications, the theoretical approach based on the maturity model was used as the basis for international standards of information technology and information security, such as ISO/IEC 15504 "Information technology - Process assessment", such as ISO/IEC 21827 "Systems security engineering - Capability maturity model" and COBIT (Control Objectives for Information and Related Technology) and URSIT (Uniform Rating System for Information Technology - Unified Assessment), as well as other information on industry or specialized standards [11].

Depending on the level of availability of information about the audited object, the following theoretical approaches are distinguished:

- o "white box" approach;
- o "gray box" approach;
- o "black box" approach.

"White box" audit is based on the fact that the auditor has complete information about the structure and operation of the audited system. For example, for an organizational system this may be information about power, formal and informal social relations; about formal rules and accepted (informal) norms of behavior. For technical systems, this may include full access to structural, functional, and electronic circuit diagrams of the equipment, as well as access to the source code of the software and accompanying documentation.

A gray box audit is based on the fact that the auditor is partially aware of the parameters of the system being studied, but information about all the principles of its operation and structure is hidden from the auditor. For example, the input and output data, the most general principles of the system's operation, and its assumed structure may be known. For an organizational system, this may only be information about the standards of management documents, official powers and responsibilities of officials without specifying the psychological characteristics of specific individuals and the norms of behavior accepted in society. For technical systems, this may include access to the input and output data of the object being studied, as well as some assumptions about the principles of operation and structure of its hardware and software.

A black box audit is based on the fact that information about the parameters, structure, and principles of operation of the system being studied is initially unavailable to the auditor.

Audit Classification

The general classification of information security audit, taking into account the above breakdown of these types of activities.

Information security audit can be classified by the following feature:

1. by the purpose of the audit;
2. by the object of the audit;
3. by the form of the audit;
4. by the practical approach to the audit;
5. by the theoretical approach to the audit;
6. by the level of impact on the audited object;
7. by the level of legality;
8. by the location of the auditor in relation to the studied system;
9. by the type of audit.

By the level of impact on the object, the audit can be divided into:

- passive;
- active.

Passive audit is the implementation of activities that do not make changes to the real object of the audit and do not transfer it to another state. Passive audit includes any type of audit based on the analysis of information security standards, as well as formal risk analysis models. If the audit includes tests based on models, then this type of audit is also classified as passive. Passive audit may also include activities related to the use of special means and methods of ITV or IPV in

an intelligence nature, aimed at collecting information about the audit object or its protection means.

Active audit includes activities related to the analysis of the reaction of the system under study or targeted impact on changing it to the required state, usually a lower security level. Active audit is testing the system with target ITI and IPV, creating incorrect or false initial data, creating an unfavorable working environment for the system, making changes to its structure or adding additional functional elements to it, which may include input data.

In the literature [1, 10], active audit is understood as any use of tools and methods for collecting information about the state of the network security subsystem, simulating the actions of an intruder/adversary. In addition, in some cases, the term "instrumental audit" is used for such active audit. However, in the author's opinion, such a terminological approach is incorrect. Not all actions to monitor network security can be classified as active audit, but only actions that use or simulate a real impact on the system under study.

According to the level of legality, audit can be divided into the following [4, 13]:

- o legal;
- o illegal.

Legal audit is distinguished by its mandatory support and, as a rule, is carried out on the basis of an agreement between the auditor and the client, which is directly related to ensuring the security of the audit object, on the development of appropriate measures.

Illegal audit is based on obtaining information about the vulnerability of the system being studied by illegal and illegitimate means. Such illegal methods include: theft, deliberate deception, wiretapping, forgery of identity documents, as well as the use of various actions containing signs of illegal behavior. Illegal activities also include inspections carried out with the participation of or by order of third parties, with the purpose of subsequently using the results of the inspection to the detriment of the system or organization being inspected.

When classifying an audit as legal and illegal, it is necessary to pay attention to the following opposite point. When conducting information operations by the relevant forces ("cyber defenders"), these operations are regulated by the internal rules of the party carrying them out. As for this party, probing enemy systems is legal. In this case, conducting such an audit is usually associated with a violation of the legislation of the party that owns the object being audited, and the audit in relation to this party is considered illegal.

Depending on the position of the auditor in relation to the system being studied, the audit can be divided into: [4, 19]:

- o external;
- o internal.

An external audit is conducted by external independent experts or using technical means and testing methods located outside the system being studied. As noted in [4, 19], as a rule, an external audit is a one-time event that is conducted at the initiative of the organization's management.

Internal audit is a continuous activity carried out by the divisions of the organization's security service using technical means of ensuring information security in accordance with the organization's regulatory documents and with the involvement of the organization's specialists.

By type of audit, audit classifications can be divided into the following [4, 9, 10]:

- *expert audit*;

- *conformity assessment:*
 - *testing;*
 - *certification;*
 - *testing:*
 - *model-based testing;*
 - *testing using special tools and methods (including instrumental audit and penetration testing);*
 - *comprehensive audit.*

Expert audit includes the process of identifying deficiencies in the system of information security measures based on the existing experience of experts participating in the audit process. During the expert audit, the state of the information security system is compared with a certain "ideal" description based on:

- requirements imposed by management during the audit process;
- description of the "ideal" security system.

As part of the expert audit, as a rule, an analysis of organizational and administrative documents is carried out, such as security policy, protection plan, various instructions, as well as projects for the implementation and improvement of the security system. These documents are assessed for compliance and conformity with the published goals and measures of information security. During this analysis, the shortcomings and weaknesses of the existing security system are identified, and comprehensive measures to improve the security level are proposed. It should be noted that during the expert audit, the results of previous surveys (including other auditors) are taken into account, design solutions and other working materials related to the creation of the information system are processed and analyzed. Detailed information on the expert audit is given in the works [4, 20].

Conformity assessment is evidence that certain requirements have been met for a product, process, system, person or body. Evidence can be direct or indirect, formal or informal. The issuance of a documentary conclusion (certificate) on compliance with the specified requirements is called confirmation of conformity. Examples of such certificates can be certificates, attestations and conclusions issued by official conformity assessment bodies. The presence of such documentary evidence distinguishes conformity assessment from other types of audits, which may not have documentary evidence in the form of a state-issued document. At the same time, the audit criteria can be more flexible, and the methods and means of its implementation - more diverse. Conformity assessment activities can be divided into the following types of activities: testing, certification, and attestation [10].

Detailed information on conformity assessment is provided in [10].

Testing is an experimental determination of the quantitative or qualitative characteristics of a test object as a result of exposure to various factors during operation or modeling. Testing is carried out on the basis of the document "Test Program and Methodology", and the test results are documented in the form of test protocols or technical reports.

Attestation is a comprehensive examination of a protected information object in real operating conditions in order to assess the compliance of protection measures and means with the required level of information security. A positive certification result is documented in the form of a certificate of conformity [10].

Certification is testing of technical means of ensuring information security, carried out by independent testing laboratories to confirm the compliance of the certification object with the requirements of regulatory documents on information security [10].

Testing is a technical operation consisting of determining one or more characteristics of a product, process or service according to the appropriate procedure [10]. Thus, the information security audit test of information systems is the determination of one or more system parameters describing a certain category of information security (for example, integrity, availability, confidentiality). Testing can be carried out to analyze risks and vulnerabilities. Based on the results of their implementation, a set of information system tests can be developed in the form of a test program with a corresponding protocol.

In general, depending on the application of a theoretical or practical approach to audit, all types of tests can be divided into:

- *model-oriented testing* - a theoretical approach to tests, when appropriate models are created and tests are carried out based on the study of these models;

- *testing with special tools and methods* - a practical approach to testing, when testing is carried out based on experiments on the impact of ITT and IPT tools and methods on the audit object or its prototype.

Comprehensive audit - includes the use of several types of audits specified above.

REFERENCES

1. Makarenko S. Ya. Information counteraction and electronic warfare in the 21st century. Monograph. – SPb.: Science-intensive technologies, 2017. – 546 p.
2. Makarenko S. Ya. Information security audit: main stages, conceptual foundations, management classification // Control, communications and security systems. 2018. No. 1. Pp. 1-29. – URL: <http://sccs.intelgr.com/archive/2018-01/01-Макаренко.pdf> (data processing: 01.06.2018).
3. Makarenko S. Ya. Information weapons in the technical sphere: terminology, classification, examples // Control, communications and security systems. 2016. No. 3. Pp. 292-376. – URL: <http://sccs.intelgr.com/archive/2016-03/11-Makarenko.pdf> (access data: 01.06.2018).
4. Averychnikov V. I., Rytov M. Yu., Kuvylkin A. V., Rudanovsky M. V. Information security audit of executive authorities: a tutorial. – M.: Flinta, 2011. – 100 p.
5. Averychnikov V. Ya. Information security audit. A tutorial for universities. – Bryansk: BSTU, 2012. – 268 p.
6. Ivanova N. V., Korobulina O. Yu. Information security audit. A tutorial. – St. Petersburg: PGUPS, 2011. – 57 p.
7. Kornienko A. A., Diasamidze S. V. Information security audit and management. Study guide. - St. Petersburg: PGUPS, 2011. - 82 p.
8. Petrenko A. A., Petrenko S. A. Internet security audit. Monograph. - Moscow: DMK Press, 2010. - 388 p.
9. Khata V. V., Shelkov A. B., Gladkov Yu. M., Pavelev S. V. Automated system for monitoring and auditing information security. - Moscow: IPU named after V. A. Trapeznikov, Russian Academy of Sciences, 2009. - 94 p.
10. Markov A. S., Tsirov V. L., Barabanov A. V. Methodology for assessing the non-compliance of information security tools / edited by KAK. Markov. – M.: Radio i svyaz, 2012. – 192 p.

11. Kurilo A. P., Zefirov S. L., Golovanov V. B. I am a doctor. Information security audit. – M.: Publishing group "BDC-press", 2006. – 304 p.
12. Moeller R. R. IT audit, control and security. – Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2010. – 667 p.
13. Skabtsov N. Information security system audit. – St. Petersburg: Piter, 2018. – 272 p.
14. Penetration testing. Procedures and methodologies. – EU-Council Press, 2011. – 237 p.
15. Kennedy D., O'Gorman J., Kearns D., Aharoni M. Metasploit. Penetration Tester's Handbook. - San Francisco: No Starch Press, 2011. - 299 p.
16. Makan K. Penetration Testing with the Bash Shell. - Birmingham: Pact Publishing, 2014. - 133 p.
17. Cardwell K. Creating Virtual Penetration Labs for Advanced Penetration Testing. - Birmingham: Pact Publishing, 2016. - 518 p.
18. Khomyakov V. A. Audit as a Method of Modernizing the Information Security System // Economic Bulletin of the Yaroslavl University. 2013. No. 29. P. 48-52.
19. Astakhov A. Introduction to Information Security Audit [Report] // GlobalTrust Solutions [Electronic resource]. 2018. – URL: <http://globaltrust.ru> (data processing: 29.01.2018).
20. Simonov S. Audit of information security system // Jet Info. 1999. No. 9 (76). P. 3-24.